

SPEECH CULTIVATION SKILLS IN THE NATIVE LANGUAGE EDUCATION OF STUDENTS

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Annotation: The complex nature of speech is that it is associated with spelling, punctuation and style. Correct writing of the word, appropriate application of punctuation marks, statement of the idea in accordance with the style requirement requires great responsibility from the reader.

Keywords: native language, children, worldview, thinking, student, thought, speech, speech activity, School, Education

Along with all subjects, the subject of mother tongue serves to expand the worldview of children, to cultivate skills and qualifications that they can think independently, listen to the opinion of others, express their thoughts flat and fluently, communicate freely with others in society. At this point, it should be noted that there will be no exaggeration even if native language education is considered not only as a school-based academic discipline, but also as a means of uniting the entire educational system.

We know that the tool that carries out the communication process of each individual is speech. Speech is the use of thinking based on the type of activity of a person, the means of language (word, vocabulary, sentence). Speech acts as interaction and message, expressing one's own opinion with emotion, and influencing others. Speech activity in the Society of all persons is considered as one of the most important means of activity of the individual. And for the student, speech is one of the important means of obtaining successful knowledge and skills in school education.

At this point, a question arises: How is the reader, in which ways can he Increase his speech? First of all, it is necessary for each reader to read more books, it is important to cultivate a spiritual worldview. Also, if the work performed by the student and his language is foreseen, speech cultivation is understood as an active practical acquisition of language in every possible way. If the teacher is envisaged, speech cultivation is understood as the application of methods and techniques that help students to actively occupy language pronunciation, vocabulary, syntactic construction and connected speech. When growing speech, three directions are clearly distinguished: 1) work on a word; 2) work on a word combination and a sentence; 3) work on connected speech. The three directions indicated are carried out in parallel: the work of the Dictionary provides material for the sentence; work on the word, vocabulary and sentence prepares for the speech with a link. In turn, linked speech serves as a means of enriching narrative and essay vocabulary.

The development of written speech is considered a much more complex process than oral speech. Because it requires readers to build the right sentence grammatically and meaningfully, to correctly apply each word in its place, to express the thought compactly, consistently, expressively, stylistically simple and fluently, to draw conclusions in the sound of

the stated thoughts. The complex nature of this discourse is further related to spelling, punctuation, and style. Correct writing of the word, appropriate application of punctuation marks, statement of the idea in accordance with the style requirement requires great responsibility from the reader. For this reason, this type of speech is much slower and more complex. Another of the peculiarities of written speech is that it can be checked, corrected, improved. In this aspect, it has much more convenient capabilities than oral speech.

The reader works on errors and shortcomings in written speech, eliminates them, seeks to avoid these mistakes and shortcomings in his later work. It should also be remembered that often students do not do enough work on the content of the text, paying great attention to spelling and punctuation marks in written work. The texts are often dominated by non-thematic opinions, with the main point being overlooked. Therefore, in native language classes, the attention of students should be paid not only to spelling and punctuation marks, but also to the fact that the stated opinion has reasonable evidence, the correct placement of the material, the correct statement of the opinion in accordance with the speaking conditions. It is necessary to create such a state in native language training so that the reader is satisfied with the text created. This inspires him to improve his speech.

If students independently think creatively and are able to correctly, fluently express the thought product in oral, written forms in accordance with the conditions of speech, then the native language training will have passed effectively. The results of the inspection carried out by the Ministry of public education of Uzbekistan, the Departments of public education of the regions, as well as our personal observations and experiments lead us to the conclusion that the level of development of students' speech is not yet in demand. Children experience more than 750 different grammatical concepts and definitions during their schooling, completing tasks of varying size and complexity around 6,500-7,000, but significant changes in their speech are noticeable. Most readers find it difficult to correctly express creative thinking, the product of thought orally and in writing; they cannot apply the rich possibilities of the Uzbek literary language in colloquial processes. To determine the reasons for this, it is necessary to separately analyze such as the factors that determine the speech development of children: their vocabulary, the skill of using vocabulary and vocabulary appropriately in a sentence, the skills of grammatically correct construction of a sentence, the skills of correct, compact, fluent, understandable statement of an idea in different speech styles.

Word poverty in students is immediately felt when it is necessary to state an opinion in oral and written form in native language classes. Repeated use of words in speech, inability to replace a given word with its meaning, same and opposite meaning, the difficulties encountered in compiling a dictionary of words belonging to a particular field, undoubtedly indicate insufficient vocabulary of readers. Another factor that makes it difficult for students to develop speech in their native language classes is that students speak Tajik, Turkmen, Kyrgyz, or other (sheva) language at home, on the street, or in extracurricular times and study in Uzbek at school. Ethnographic data indicate that a huge number of Tajiks, Turkmen, Kyrgyz, Kazakhs live on the territory of our republic. Many of them spoke Tajik, Kyrgyz, etc at home and studied Uzbek at school. This circumstance undoubtedly limits the possibility of free expression of one's own opinion in readers, taking advantage of the rich possibilities of language.

In addition to the negative factors listed above, the content and content of work carried out from our native language outside of class and school negatively affects the development of

oral and written speech by students, such as not always following the unified Speech regime, insufficient work of parents on child speech. Thus, the development of student speech is a complex process, and the factors that make money on it also do not depend solely on the content of education or the teacher. The process of teaching a person to correctly, fluently express an opinion, both verbally and in writing, is easy if all the possibilities are fully worked out. Opens a wide path to the development of the reader's speech. As we know, students are bored with homogeneity. Therefore, when growing their speech, it is necessary to constantly use different methods and games.

The above points serve to facilitate and strengthen the process of mastering knowledge, as well as to increase the activity of students in the lesson, and to create an interesting organization of each activity aimed at growing speech. The idea of liberalizing our society is directly embodied in the educational process, which is ensured on the basis of its new organization and change of content, further humanization, socialization and democratization.

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